

OPTIMIZATION OF LAMP POSITIONS IN THE UV CURING OF 3-DIMENSIONAL COMPOSITE COMPONENTS MANUFACTURED USING THE RIDFT PROCESS

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Abstract

A simple method for locating optimal positions for UV lamps used in the curing of curvilinear composite components manufactured with the Resin Infusion between Double Flexible Tooling (RIDFT) process is proposed. A multivariate optimization model, consisting of continuously differentiable and two-dimensional integral domain parts was developed. This model has UV lamps positions, dimensions of the manufactured composite component, and UV power source as the input parameters. The optimum positions of the UV lamps are the output. The two-dimensional integration yields the difference between the required intensity and actual intensity the composite component receives. A Gauss quadrature numerical integration method was used to numerically evaluate the surface integral, and the Davidon-Fletcher-Powell (DFP) algorithm was used for predicting optimum positions for the lamps. Mechanical and rheological properties of the UV cured laminates were compared with catalytically cured laminates. UV cured components compared well with the catalytic cured composites.

Keywords: Resin infusion; Forming; UV curing; Rheology; Optimization

INTRODUCTION

UV curing, also known as photo-curing reduces the curing time of composite materials from hours to minutes. It was first patented in 1947 and commercialized in 1960 within the furniture industry [1]. It provides a consistent and controlled process as compared to the classical catalyst method for composite curing, whose resulting product will vary according to the humidity and temperature of the curing environment. As such, the UV curing market has grown at double-digit rates in the last decade [2]. Curing of polymer matrices by UV may be applicable to any composite manufacturing process provided the UV rays can directly illuminate the component or in cases where the component is enclosed in a vacuum bag or membrane, the membrane should be transparent to UV rays.

The utilization of UV curing has been demonstrated with the Resin Infusion between Double Flexible Tooling (RIDFT) process for flat components [3]. However, the curing of three-dimensional components till today remains a challenge to the composite manufacturing industry. Applying UV curing to curvilinear geometries usually requires utilization of several lamps positioned around the component. Not only is this expensive, but it may allow for UV exposure overlap, resulting in excessive curing of some areas on the component. Trial-and-error positioning, utilization of large arrays of UV lamps with components moving on a conveyor, and robotically actuated UV lamps have been employed in some quarters [4-7]. These methods are too expensive, time consuming, and complex for the RIDFT process, thus negating the idea of simplicity that the RIDFT composite manufacturing process tends to portray [3]. To tackle this problem, a general-purpose model was proposed.

MATHEMATICAL MODEL FOR UV CURING PROBLEM

Application of UV radiation to the curing of composite materials can be mathematically modeled using the fundamental principles of electromagnetic radiation. The simplified mathematical model is based on simple power emission neglecting many of the UV curing parameters such as temperature, wavelength and angle of incidence. The aim was to minimize the difference between the average intensity required to cure three-dimensional composite substrates and the actual intensity radiated from the UV source. Several factors affect depth of cure in the UV curing of polymer composites. These include composition of the material (translucency), choice and composition of photoinitiators, wavelength of the curing light, intensity, and irradiation time. Apart from intensity and irradiation time, all other effects were ignored in the model. Among all these factors, intensity plays the major role [8]. Curing can only be initiated when the photoinitiators attract the minimum amount of UV radiation, with an appropriate wavelength, necessary to commence chemical reaction in the resin.

Consider Figure 1, showing a composite structure to be cured and defined as the surface domain γ such that $\gamma \in \mathfrak{R}^3$ where the point \mathbf{p} belongs to γ with a surface normal \mathbf{n} . The source of the UV light is given by the coordinate point $\mathbf{s} \in \mathfrak{R}^3$. The objective function $F(\mathbf{s})$ to be minimized is defined as the difference between the desired intensity and the actual intensity and will be mathematically defined in Equation (8). As with all optimization problems, the purpose is to minimize the objective function $F(\mathbf{s})$ by varying the independent variable, \mathbf{s} , expressed simply as:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Min } F(\mathbf{s}) & \hspace{15em} 1 \\ \mathbf{s} \in \mathfrak{R}^3 & \end{aligned}$$

The direction vector between the surface and the light source is defined as \mathbf{d} and is expressed as:

$$\mathbf{d} \equiv \mathbf{s} - \mathbf{p}$$

Figure 1 Coordinate system for a point on a composite material and a light source

The UV lamp is treated as a point source of electromagnetic radiation with intensity $I(\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{s})$. The intensity from the light source is inversely proportional to the square of the distance from the source to the surface to be cured (see e.g., [9] for the classical description), expressed as:

$$I_{source}(\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{s}) = \frac{P}{4\pi(r(\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{s}))^2} \quad 3$$

Where $r(\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{s})$ is the magnitude of the direction vector \mathbf{d} , and P is the power (in Watts) from the UV light source. This magnitude, $r(\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{s})$ is expressed as:

$$r(\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{s}) = \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^3 (s_i - p_i)^2} \quad 4$$

The intensity expressed in Equation (3) assumes the surface is normal to the source at which the incident light emits from, which is often not the case. The actual light intensity on the point \mathbf{p} on the surface γ is proportional to the normal intensity multiplied by the dot product between the surface normal vector and the source direction vector:

$$I(\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{s}) = \begin{cases} \frac{P}{4\pi} \frac{1}{(r(\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{s}))^2} \mathbf{n}(\mathbf{p}) \cdot \frac{\mathbf{d}(\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{s})}{r(\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{s})} & \mathbf{n} \cdot \mathbf{d} \geq 0 \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad 5$$

where the later component of Equation (5) is given with the understanding that when the surface normal points away from the source no light is incident on the surface, i.e. the surface cannot be heated when it faces away from the light source. For simplicity, with the understanding that light cannot pass through the back edge of the surface, Equation (5) may be rewritten in the following way:

$$I(\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{s}) = \frac{P}{4\pi r^3} \sum_{i=1}^3 n_i d_i \quad 6$$

Equations (2) and (6) can be combined into a single expression with explicit s dependence as:

$$I(\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{s}) = \frac{P}{4\pi} \frac{1}{r^3} \sum_{i=1}^3 (n_i s_i - n_i p_i)$$

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Let \bar{E} be the desired optimal curing intensity. For even curing to take place over the cured component surface, the absolute value of the difference between the desired intensity for curing \bar{E} and the actual intensity $I(\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{s})$, given in Equation (7), must be as close to zero as possible. To avoid taking the derivative of an absolute value, the approximation $|x| \approx x^2$ is made in further expressions recognizing that both functions share the same desired characteristic in that all values are positive and they share the same minimum. Thus the objective function of minimization alluded to in Equation (1) is defined as:

$$F(\mathbf{s}) = \oint_{\gamma} (\bar{E} - I(\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{s}))^2 d\gamma$$

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where the integrand is integrated over all space to yield, in a sense, the spatial average squared behavior between the actual and the desired surface intensity. To find the minimum of the objective function with respect to the lamp position \mathbf{s} , the gradient is required where the j^{th} component is expressed simply as:

$$\frac{\partial F}{\partial s_j} = \frac{\partial}{\partial s_j} \oint_{\gamma} (\bar{E} - I(\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{s}))^2 d\gamma$$

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Note that both \bar{E} and the surface of integration are independent of s_j (the lamp position), thus using the chain rule Equation (9) may be expressed as:

$$\frac{\partial F}{\partial s_j} = -2 \oint_{\gamma} (\bar{E} - I(\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{s})) \left(\frac{\partial I(\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{s})}{\partial s_j} \right) d\gamma$$

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Taking the derivative of the intensity expressed in Equation (7) (where it is noted that the dependence r has on \mathbf{s} is retained) yields

$$\frac{\partial I}{\partial s_j} = \frac{P}{4\pi} \left(\frac{n_j}{r^3} - \frac{3 \sum_{i=1}^3 (n_i s_i - n_i p_i)}{r^4} \frac{\partial r}{\partial s_j} \right)$$

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The partial on r in Equation (11) is expressed as

$$\frac{\partial r(\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{s})}{\partial s_j} = (s_i s_i + p_i p_i - 2s_i p_i)^{-1/2} (2s_j - 2p_j)$$

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Substituting Equation (12) into Equation (11) and simplifying the expression, yields j^{th} component of the gradient of the objective function to be used in the optimization scheme as

$$\frac{\partial F(\mathbf{s})}{\partial s_j} = -2 \oint_{\gamma} \left(\bar{E} - \frac{P}{4\pi r^3} \sum_{k=1}^3 n_k (s_k - p_k) \right) \frac{P}{4\pi r^3} \left(n_j - \frac{3(s_j - p_j)}{r^2} \sum_{i=1}^3 (n_i s_i - n_i p_i) \right) d\gamma$$

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SOLUTION PROCEDURE

An analytical approach to finding the optimum value(s) of Equation (1) is typically desired, but due to the expected geometric complexities of the surface γ for typical industrial products, and the desire to establish an automated procedure to be used in an industrial setting, we will resort to numerical solution procedures. There exist many numerical integration methods from which to choose, i.e. Simpson 1/3 rule, Simpson 3/8 rule, Trapezoidal rule, Newton-Cotes formula, and Gauss Quadrature [10]. In the present work, Gauss Quadrature was selected for both its simplicity and increased accuracy over the classical Newton-Cotes methods involving an equivalent number of integration points. There are two basic components required to minimize the objective function expressed in Equation (8). The first component is developing an algorithm to numerically evaluate the integrands expressed in Equations (8) and (13), and the second is to employ a classical numerical optimization algorithm that will iteratively search for a local minimum. Davidon-Fletcher-Powell (DFP) algorithm was applied to Equation (13).

A simple test was performed to demonstrate the effectiveness of the Gauss Quadrature approach for the integrations. A square plate like the one shown in Figure 2 measuring 2 x 2 units was used. An imaginary UV lamp with 50W power was allowed to shine at the square plate at different positions in space. The x and y components of the UV lamp were changed while the z component was kept constant. The desired intensity required \bar{E} needed to cure the flat plate was set to 2W/unit² (Equation (8)). These values with the lamp positions and the dimension of the plate were used in Equations (5 and 8). Equation (8) was analytically evaluated using Mathematica. The value of s_z was kept constant at 1.2 units while s_x and s_y values changed from 0 to 2 units with an increment of 0.5. The results obtained analytically for Equation (8) are similar to the results obtained for the Gauss quadrature numerical integration. Details of these results are given in [11].

Figure 2 Schematic of a composite plate being UV-cured

Color plots for Equation (5) and Equation (8) at the maximum are shown in Figures 3a and 3b respectively. In Figure 3a, the red portion of the plots shows the area

where the intensity is the highest. Other parts of the plate received lower amount of intensity. Figure 3b shows the intensity difference as indicated by the objective function. The blue portion of the plate shows the area having minimum difference between the actual intensity and the desired intensity. Figures 4a and 4b respectively show the intensity distribution and intensity difference at the optimum lamp position. As shown, the difference between the desired and the actual intensity has greatly reduced when compared with Figure 3b. This situation occurred when the lamp was positioned at (1,1,1.2).

Figure 3 (a) Intensity distribution at the at the maximum (at lamp position (0,0,1.2))(b) Intensity difference at the at the maximum (at lamp position (0,0,1.2))

Figure 4 (a) Intensity distribution at the at the minimum (at lamp position (1,1,1.2))(b) Intensity difference at the at the minimum (at lamp position (1,1,1.2))

Experimental Methodology

Materials

The reinforcement material used for the experiments was BGF 7781 satin weave E-Glass fiber. The resin used in this work was an epoxy-based vinyl ester (Derakane 470–45). Two molds were used. The fabrics used in Mold 1 were cut to 27.9cm x 25.4cm (11in x 10in), and fabrics for Mold 2 were cut to 38.1 x 22.9 (15in x 9in). Two levels of fiber layers (10 and 15) were used in the experiments.

The vinyl ester resin was converted into a photoinitiated (light curing) resin by the addition of two photoinitiators, the phenylbis (2,4,6-trimethylbenzoyl)-phosphine oxide (BAPO) and the alpha hydroxyl ketone oxide (AHK). Both photoinitiators are manufactured by Ciba Specialty Chemicals Inc., and go by the brand names Irgacure 819 and Irgacure 184 respectively [12]. BAPO delivers complete through cure of thick sections. The concentration of this photoinitiator in a UV curable resin is between 0.5 to 3%. It is highly recommended for applications where cure speed, through cure, low odor, and low emission are of great importance. BAPO was designed to be activated by longer wavelength (about 400nm). Longer wavelength, though with lower photon energy, penetrates deeper into the parts to be cured than shorter wavelength UV light, which are used for surface curing only. AHK which is a highly efficient nonyellowing photoinitiator used to initiate the photopolymerization of chemically unsaturated prepolymers in combination with mono or multifunctional vinyl monomers was also used in this work. AHK is particularly useful for obtaining good surface quality. To obtain a balance between surface and through curing, a number of photo initiators can be combined with Irgacure 819. A photoinitiator of the alpha hydroxyketone class (such as Irgacure 184) are specifically useful as a combination for Irgacure 819 to ensure the correct level of surface cure. AHK is activated at the wavelengths in the 200nm range. This photoinitiator is used most of the times as co-initiator to balance through and surface cure.

The first resin/photoinitiator combination was formulated with one photoinitiator – BAPO. The weight of a petri dish was determined; BAPO that measured up to 2% of the weight of the resin was placed in the petri dish before being added to the resin. The second resin/photoinitiator combination was formulated with a combination of BAPO and AHK in ratio 1:3, having a total weight representing 1% of the weight of the resin.

Lamp Positions

The input variables into the function (Equation 8) include the positions of the composite components (\mathbf{p}) on the RIDFT machine, the positions of the lamps in space(s), the power from the UV source(P), the desired intensity (\bar{E}), and the unit normal to the surface (\mathbf{n}). Two types of molds called Mold 1 and Mold 2 (Figures 5 and 6) were used.

Figure 5 Mold 1

Figure 6 Mold 2

The dimensions of these molds were used (Equations 5, 8, and 13) to locate the position of the composite substrate on the RIDFT equipment. Two power levels were

used on the UV (360W and 600W). These two power levels with the two molds used gave four possible positions for the lamps (2^2). Three different manufacturing designs were developed. Each of these designs was tested using two different lamp positions to determine the effect these suggested positions have on the mechanical properties of the manufactured three-dimensional composites. These manufacturing designs were set up by considering the composition of photoinitiators, number of fiber layers, and irradiation time. Two different levels of each of these factors were considered. The experimental design used is given in Table 1.

Experiments for the UV curing of three-dimensional composite substrates were performed using the materials and molds described in the preceding subsections. Catalytic cured three-dimensional composite substrates were also made to serve as benchmark for comparison with the UV cured laminates. UV power level and the dimensions of the molds were the parameters used to suggest the positions of the two UV lamps. Lamps were set at the suggested positions from the model at the onset of each experiment. After determining the positions of the lamps, photoinitiated resin was infused in the fiber-filled RIDFT equipment.

Table 1 Experimental Design Matrix

Lamp Position	Manufacturing Design	Factors	Quantity
1: (Mold 1: 60% Power Level:360W)	1	Fiber Layers	10
		Photoinitiator Composition	1:3(BAPO&AHK)
		Irradiation Time	120
2 (Mold 1: 100% Power Level:600W)	2	Fiber Layers	15
		Photoinitiator Composition	BAPO
		Time	90
3 (Mold 2: 60% Power Level: 360W)	3	Fiber Layers	10
		Photoinitiator Composition	BAPO
		Irradiation Time	120
4 (Mold 2: 100% Power Level: 600W)	1	Fiber Layers	10
		Photoinitiator Composition	1:3(BAPO&AHK)
		Irradiation Time	120

The desired three-dimensional shape was then formed. The UV lamps were turned on for a specified duration of time. At the expiration of the irradiation time, the parts were demolded from the RIDFT equipment and prepared for tensile and rheological testing.

Results

Mathematical Model Results

The main objective of this paper is to demonstrate the ability to locate the optimum lamp positions for curing of three-dimensional composite components by minimizing the difference between the required and the actual intensities. Initial lamp positions used with the optimization model (Equation 13) are shown in Table 2. The UV curing system used for this purpose consists of two identical UV lamps that are

suspended in space at the initial location shown in the table. The geometries used are Molds 1 and 2. Mold 1 has a flat top with four slanted sides. The mold is 15cm × 14cm × 7cm. Mold 2 is tapered in shape with slightly curved tip. It is 28cm × 9cm × 6cm. The geometries of these molds, the initial positions of the UV lamps, and UV power level were the input values into the model.

DFP algorithm was used to perform series of iterations while testing the convergence of the objective function to a particular tolerance level at the end of each iteration. When the desired tolerance level is reached, the positions of the UV lamps at that point become the optimum positions. For example, when the UV power level was set to 100% and the geometry for the composite components was Mold 2. The initial lamp positions were set to $s_1 = (30,10,40)$ and $s_2 = (-30,-15,40)$. After nine successive iterations, the minimum value for the objective function was obtained at the positions $s_1 = (44.18, 10.95, 64.41)$ and $s_2 = (-21.61, -0.87, 48.93)$. These positions are the optimum positions for that particular geometry, power level and initial lamp positions. The value of the objective function for this particular case is shown in Figure 6 for each iteration during the optimization procedure. As observed in Figure 6, the value of the objective function decreases after each successive iteration. Details of the combination of initial lamp positions, and composite component geometry and the UV power level with their optimum positions are given in Table 2.

Table 2: Optimized UV Lamp Positions

S/N	Mold type	Power level (Watts)	Initial Position of the two lamps (cm)	Suggested final positions of the two lamps (cm)
1	Mold1	360	(20,18,40) and (-20,-17,40)	(15.72, 6.71,10.09) and (-23.96,-35.26,35.92)
2			(22,20,40) and (-22,-20,40)	(27.88,31.93,67.83) and (-17.77,-2.89,42.86)
1		600	(20,18,40) and (-20,-17,40)	(23.33,26.32,63.17) and (-16.88,-3.03,43.77)
2			(24,20,40) and (-24,-20,40)	(32.26,32.55,69.44) and (-18.86,-1.77,42.85)
1	Mold 2	360	(30,10,40) and (-30,-15,40)	(42.18,10.95,64.41) and (-21.61,-0.87,48.94)
2			(30,10,40) and (-30,-20,40)	(44.98,11.17,70.03) and (-19.69,-2.62,50.98)
1		600	(30,10,40) and (-30,-15,40)	(42.18,10.95,64.41) and (-21.61,-0.87,48.93)
2			(30,10,40) and (-30,-20,40)	(44.95,11.17,69.97) and (-19.71,-2.65,50.96)

Figure 6 Function minimization plot

The two-UV lamp system was used on a box-like geometry representing the two molds used in the experiments. A preliminary set of solutions was obtained from the model.

These solutions were used to set up the experimental conditions shown in Table 1. Initial and final lamp positions were suggested for the experiments and these were used in Equation (5) to generate the intensity distribution on the manufactured composite substrates. A typical intensity distribution is shown in Figure 7. This represents the intensity distribution on Mold 1, with the power level set at 60% (360W) for the initial and final positions of the UV lamps. For this case, the maximum intensity decreased from $0.02\text{W}/\text{cm}^2$ at the initial position to $0.012\text{W}/\text{cm}^2$ at the final lamp positions.

Figure 7 Graphs of Intensity Distribution on Mold1 at 60% UV Power Level (a) Initial lamp position (b) Final lamp position

Although, all the faces are not uniformly cured, the intensity values for each of the faces are relatively evenly distributed for the final lamp positions as depicted in intensity distribution figure shown above. For example, in Figure 7(a), the top of the box is red, decreasing from point (15,14,7) to point (0,0,7). The lamp was very close to the first point, thus it received the highest intensity. Ordinarily, the positive z face of the box (top) and the tip of the box at negative x and negative y faces should have had the same color mapping, but there was a sharp color difference among these faces due to the direction of the surface normal between the two faces.

When the power input for Mold 1 was increased to 100% of the UV system capacity (Figure 8), the maximum intensity value for the initial lamp position increased by 25% because more power was given off from the source. An increase in maximum intensity of 33% at the final UV lamp positions was noted. The difference between the maximum and minimum intensity distribution per face was less than 15%.

Figure 8 Intensity Distribution on Mold1 at 100% UV Power Level (a) Initial lamp position (b) Final lamp position

In Figure 9, there was no sharp difference between the highest intensity value in both the initial and final lamp positions. The intensity distributions at various sides of the box in this set-up are much closer compared with other set-ups.

Figure 9 Intensity Distribution on Mold2 at 60% UV Power Level (a) Initial lamp position (b) Final lamp position

Rheological and Tensile Tests Results

Experiments were performed using the design shown in Table 1. Some of the lamp positions used in plotting the color contours shown in Figures 7 to 9 were used in the experiments. Each manufacturing design was cured using two different lamp positions. Manufacturing Design 1 was cured with Lamp positions 1 and 4. Manufacturing Designs 2 and 3 were cured using positions 2 and 3. Catalytic cured composite materials were manufactured using 5, 10, and 15 layers of fibers. The summaries of results from rheological and tensile tests are shown in Tables 3 and 4 respectively.

Table 3 Summary of the Rheological Properties and the Manufacturing Designs

Lamp Position	Manufacturing Design 1		Manufacturing Design 2		Manufacturing Design 3	
	T _g (°C)	Storage Modulus (GPa)	T _g (°C)	Storage Modulus (GPa)	T _g (°C)	Storage Modulus (GPa)
1	102.51	8.65				
2			137.60	10.74	139.44	10.24
3			142.59	14.05	142.79	15.42
4	107.00	13.39				
Catalytic Cured Composites						
5 Layers of Fiber			103.67	6.50		
10 Layers of Fiber			104.75	11.05		
15 Layers of Fiber			109.65	31.40		

From Tables 3 and 4, it can be observed that the tensile and rheological properties of the laminates from Lamp position 3 are superior to the rest including the catalytically cured laminates. Even distribution of UV light on the geometry used for this position might be responsible for this relatively superior mechanical properties. This is still subject to further investigation. Overall, the UV cured laminates have better properties than the catalytically cured ones, and this may be attributed to the speed of the UV curing which helps to trap styrene molecules that would ordinarily have been

lost through evaporation making them available to help drive the polymerization curing reaction [3, 13].

Table 4 Summary of Tensile Test Results

Lamp Position	Manufacturing Design 1		Manufacturing Design 2		Manufacturing Design 3	
	Tensile Strength (MPa)	Young's Modulus (GPa)	Tensile Strength (MPa)	Young's Modulus (GPa)	Tensile Strength (MPa)	Young's Modulus (GPa)
1	141.23	11.16				
2			157.02	10.74	196.85	11.14
3			269.04	17.86	205.24	15.65
4	208.16	22.41				
Catalytic Cured Composites						
5 Layers of Fiber			81.02	13.73		
10 Layers of Fiber			164.48	13.76		
15 Layers of Fiber			181.95	18.22		

Figures 10 and 11 respectively show summaries of the tensile strength and the Young's modulus of the different manufacturing designs compared with each other. The results indicate better mechanical properties from the composites manufactured using Mold 2. Tensile properties of lamp positions with higher UV power level are much higher than those of lower UV lamp power level in the first design.

Figure 10 Tensile strength summary by lamp position

Figure 11 Young's modulus summary by lamp position

Conclusion

In this work, an attempt was made to provide analytically, a means of locating UV lamps for optimal curing of curvilinear composite laminates using the RIDFT process. A multivariate optimization model, consisting of a continuously differentiable and a two-dimensional integral domain parts was developed. The solution to the model is in two stages: numerical solution to the two-dimensional integral domain using Gauss quadrature method and solution to the optimization problem using Davidon-Fletcher

Powell (DFP) algorithm. The goal of the model was to predict the optimum positions for UV lamps.

Three different types of manufacturing designs were identified. Four predicted lamp positions were used. Each manufacturing design was tested using two different lamp positions. The results were compared with each other and it was found that Lamp position 3 yielded the best mechanical properties. This predicted position resulted in mechanical properties superior to the catalytically cured laminates. Nonetheless, uniform curing is yet to be obtained over the entire component geometry. As such, further work is required to achieve the goals of this work.

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